

On the purported representation of *Haliphron atlanticus* (Cephalopoda: Octopoda: Alloposidae) on Mycenaean funerary gold ornaments

Sobre la supuesta representación de *Haliphron atlanticus* (Cephalopoda: Octopoda: Alloposidae) en adornos de oro funerarios micénicos

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ABSTRACT

The common octopus, *Octopus vulgaris* Cuvier, 1797, is widely depicted in Minoan and Mycenaean craftworks from the Late Bronze Age (ca. 1900-1100 BC). Some octopus-shaped funerary gold ornaments from a Mycenaean grave, all of them displaying seven arms, were supposed to portray the so-called seven-armed octopus, *Haliphron atlanticus* Steenstrup, 1861 (Octopoda: Argonautoidea: Alloposidae). Here it is shown that in fact those octopus-like ornaments cannot represent *H. atlanticus* because of morphological as well as biogeographical and ecological reasons.

RESUMEN

El pulpo común, *Octopus vulgaris* Cuvier, 1797, está ampliamente representado en las artesanías minoicas y micénicas de la Edad de Bronce tardía (ca. 1900-1100 a. C.). Se suponía que algunos adornos funerarios de oro en forma de pulpo de una tumba micénica, todos ellos con siete brazos, representaban el llamado pulpo de siete brazos, *Haliphron atlanticus* Steenstrup, 1861 (Octopoda: Argonautoidea: Alloposidae). En este trabajo se demuestra que esos adornos con forma de pulpo no son representaciones de *H. atlanticus* debido a razones morfológicas, biogeográficas y ecológicas.

KEY WORDS: Aegean Bronze Age, funerary ornaments, Mediterranean Sea, *Octopus vulgaris*, *Haliphron atlanticus*.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Edad del Bronce del Egeo, adornos funerarios, Mar Mediterráneo, *Octopus vulgaris*, *Haliphron atlanticus*.

INTRODUCTION

Among the several sea creatures represented in many different media from the Aegean Bronze Age (pottery, painting, jewellery, mosaic, stone carving, and so on) as well as in later craftworks

(including coins) from the same geographic area, a peculiar symbolic place has been held by the octopus (e.g. PREZIOSI AND HITCHCOCK 1999; PUGLISI 2004; ALBERTI 2013). As for the octopus

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species depicted in Minoan and Mycenaean craftworks from the Late Bronze Age (ca. 1900-1100 BC), ALBERTI AND BELLO (in press) show that it is the Mediterranean common octopus, *Octopus vulgaris* Cuvier, 1797 (Cephalopoda: Octopoda: Octopodidae), one of the 13 autochthonous octopod species living in this basin (BELLO 2003).

HARTMAN (2014a), focussing her attention on a group of similar octopus-shaped funerary gold ornaments from a Mycenaean grave, all of them displaying seven arms, supposed that they represented the so-called seven-armed octopus, *Haliphron atlanticus* Steenstrup, 1861 (Octopoda: Argonautoidea: Alloposidae). HARTMAN (2014b), in order to corroborate her hypothesis, produced additional purported probative elements relating to the biology and ecology of octopods as well as other marine creatures. In this note it is shown that the hypothesis by HARTMAN (2014a, b), concerning the presence of *Haliphron atlanticus* in the Bronze Age Mediterranean Sea, is not supported by any scientific data.

THE 7-ARMED MYCENAEAN OCTOPUS

The octopus-shaped gold ornaments dealt with by HARTMAN (2014a, b) were found in Grave IV of the Grave Circle A in Mycenae (Argolid, Greece), which is dated to the XVI century BC (PREZIOSI AND HITCHCOCK 1999). HARTMAN (2014b) reported that the National Archaeological Museum in Athens holds in display 41 of the 53 original gold leaves figuring a seven-armed octopus, each of them 6.8 cm wide. The octopus-shaped ornaments were most probably sewn on the shroud enveloping the deceased thanks to the eyelets formed by their curled arm tips (GAGNÉ 2004).

It is quite evident that the animal represented in these gold ornaments is an octopus, which may be described in biological terms as a naturalistically

figured octopodid, i.e. a member of the family Octopodidae, that shows the dorsal side of the body (mantle or sac + head) and the oral, i.e. suckered, side of the arms. The description may further include that the arms are comparatively long with respect to the body size, bear one row of suckers and are devoid of interbrachial web; the mantle is elongate, diamond-shaped; the animal has only seven arms. The latter character might appear as a great oddity to people that know that actual octopuses have eight arms. And indeed, it appeared a “nagging anomaly” to HARTMAN (2014b). Teuthologists, i.e. workers on cephalopods, would point out additional oddities, such as the presence of only one row of suckers on comparatively long arms, which characters conflict with each other since one sucker row is typical of short-armed octopodids (e.g. members of the genus *Eledone*; cf. NORMAN, FINN AND HOCHBERG 2016), and the unnatural position of the animal, with its arms twisted so that all suckers are on display. However, all these ostensible anomalies completely lose their noteworthiness when one, be he/she a lay person or a teuthologist, ponders that this gold ornament is an artwork. In fact, there are some other Mycenaean burial gold ornaments that figure octopuses with six and eight arms, either symmetrically or asymmetrically set (GAGNÉ 2004).

THE ACTUAL “SEVEN-ARMED OCTOPUS”: *HALIPHRON ATLANTICUS*

Haliphron atlanticus – i.e. the octopod supposed by HARTMAN (2014a, b) to be that figured in the Mycenaean gold ornaments – is a gelatinous pan-oceanic deep-sea pelagic octopod (GUERRA 1992; FINN 2016; YOUNG 2016) that was never reported in the Mediterranean Sea (see negative evidence in GUERRA 1992 and BELLO 2003). This species is characterized, as are all members of Argonautoidea, by a marked sexual dimorphism: the male is dwarfed and may reach a

Figure 1. The seven-armed octopus figured in a Mycenaean gold ornament. Left: drawing by HARTMAN (2014b); right: the actual brooch (after CARTWRIGHT 2014).

Figura 1. El pulpo de siete brazos figurado en un adorno de oro micénico. Izquierda: dibujo de HARTMAN (2014b); derecha: el broche real (reproducido de CARTWRIGHT 2014).

maximum total length of about 30 cm (YOUNG 2016), whereas the female is much larger and can grow up to 4 m total length and 45 kg in weight (O'SHEA 2004).

As regards the present issue, the males of all argonautoid species hold their copulatory arm, the hectocotylus, coiled in a pouch under either the right eye (genera *Haliphron*, *Ocythoe* and *Tremoctopus*) or the left eye (genus *Argonauta*). Hence, they appear to have only seven arms, except when they copulate and the hectocotylus is unfolded out of its pouch to be detached at mating (YOUNG 2016). This character caused the *H. atlanticus* male, hence the species, to be popularly named 'seven-armed octopus.' Indeed, the FAO official English name is 'gelatinous giant octopod' (FINN 2016), therefore the vernacular name 'seven-armed' (or 'seven-arm') is not endorsed by FAO and should not be used, especially in scientific publications, since misleading.

On that account, when looking for the actual seven-armed individuals of *H. atlanticus*, one has to take into consideration only the males of the species. The image itself of this animal (cf. YOUNG 2016: fig. "Oral views of three males") is sufficient to deter any attribution of the octopod figured in the Mycenaean gold ornaments to *H. atlanticus*.

One may note in the male of this species the very short mantle, the absence of any narrowing between the head and both the mantle and the arms, the deep interbranchial web, the comparatively short arm length, and the presence of two sucker rows on the arms (cf. also FINN 2016). Moreover, the octopus depicted in the Mycenaean ornaments displays four right and three left arms, whereas in the actual male *H. atlanticus* it is an arm from the right side (the third one) to be hectocotylized and hidden in a pouch. All these characters clearly disclaim any ascribing of the Mycenaean gold ornament seven-armed octopus to the male of *H. atlanticus*.

In summary, both the geographical distribution and, most importantly, the morphology of the male of *H. atlanticus* dismiss HARTMAN's (2014a, b) hypothesis.

ADDITIONAL INCONGRUENCES IN HARTMAN (2014B)

HARTMAN's paper (2014b) suffers several incongruences and oversimplifications. She stated that *H. atlanticus* "is the largest octopus in the world, weighing around 45 kilos, and measuring 4 meters in length." This is not true since, for instance, the North-Pacific octopus

Enteroctopus dofleini (Wülker, 1910) (Octopoda: Enteroctopodidae) can weigh more than 180 kg (NORMAN ET AL. 2016).

More astonishingly, HARTMAN (2014b) mentioned the present day intensified marine harvesting in close association with old time reports of very large fishes to freely extrapolate that in ancient times *H. atlanticus* weighed twice present-day individuals, i.e. 90 kg. It is well known that many long-lived marine animals are presently suffering size-overfishing, but short-lived animals, such as cephalopods, are not affected by this phenomenon.

As for the occurrence of *H. atlanticus* in the Mediterranean Sea, HARTMAN (2014b) stated that “Due to *H. atlanticus*’ current global range and robust stature, it is likely that the 7-armed octopus once inhabited the Mediterranean”, a bold statement that in fact is devoid of any biological support, since there are many pan-oceanic species, both large- and small-sized, that do not live in the Mediterranean Sea. HARTMAN (2014b) explained the assumed disappearance of *H. atlanticus* from this sea by overfishing. In fact, *H. atlanticus* has never been collected for human food in any part of the world because of its rarity and, most of all, because it is not edible, hence it could never be overharvested.

In support of her side hypothesis that *H. atlanticus* once was a member of the Mediterranean fauna, HARTMAN (2014b) also reported that “Pliny the Elder strengthens the probability that the 7-armed octopus was at one time native to the region when he reported that Trebius Niger knew about a large octopus, its head alone being “as big as a cask [which] held 90 gallons” (Pli. Nat. 9.48). Due to its size, it can be nothing but an *H. atlanticus*. This particular specimen repeatedly stole fish from the coastal town of Carteia (Pli. NH. 9.48). It “was in the habit of getting into [the fishermen’s] uncovered tanks...and there foraging for salted fish.” (Pli. NH. 9.48)” (square brackets are HARTMAN’S, 2014b). In fact, Trebius Niger’s reports were deemed rather suspicious; at best they might be labelled exaggerated

(BELLO 2011). Anyway, *H. atlanticus*, besides being an oceanic cephalopod dwelling far away from the coast, could not move on dry land without the support of water because of the gelatinous texture of its body, hence for sure it was not the fish stealer.

Incidentally, the first octopus figuration appears in a series of vases belonging to the so-called Kamares Style, at the beginning of the 2nd millennium BC (ALBERTI AND BELLO in press), which is well before the middle of the XVI century BC, the age claimed by HARTMAN (2014b) when the octopus first made its appearance in Crete.

CONCLUSIONS

It is quite evident that the octopus depicted in hundreds of shapes on hundreds and hundreds of Minoan and Mycenaean craftworks, including the seven-armed octopus-shaped gold ornaments from Grave IV of the Grave Circle A at Mycenae, is the common Mediterranean octopus *Octopus vulgaris* (GILL 1985; ALBERTI AND BELLO in press) and not the oceanic *Haliphron atlanticus*, extraneous to the Mediterranean.

It is also evident that octopus depictions have varied diachronically and diatopically, both in style and number of tentacles (GAGNÉ 2004; ALBERTI 2013; ALBERTI AND BELLO in press), also according to the medium carrying the figuration (e.g. on small sized seals, octopuses are stylized with only two or three pairs or arms because of intrinsic space limitations; GILL 1985). The octopus motif is later on found also in Magna Grecian and Italiote craftworks (e.g. PUGLISI 2004; BELLO 2011). Therefore, we cannot expect that the seven-armed octopus figured in Mycenaean gold ornaments to be a precise naturalistic representation. For sure it was not meant to be that.

Most probably the goldsmith who crafted the series of 53 equal leaves intended that people looking at them both promptly realized that they represented the octopus – without bothering counting neither the arms, whether

eight or seven, nor the rows of suckers – and would value the artisan’s skill as well as the dead person’s wealth. In this respect, GAGNÉ (2004) pointed out that the artists who worked with gold, because of its cost, were most likely highly skilled and were expected to produce ornamental and possibly symbolic artworks of the highest possible quality. We can assume that people who requested goldsmiths to craft the gold octopus-shaped ornaments meant to honour their soon-to-be-buried relative by means of precious symbolic objects (in addition to the many other objects to accompany the dead into that grave).

In short, all Aegean Bronze Age octopus figurations are just abstractions and stylization of reality meant to convey symbolic/spiritual meaning(s). Much has been written about octopus representations in the Minoan and

Mycenaean cultural worlds, as well as in those that from them derived, including its symbolic significance (e.g. GILL 1985; PREZIOSI AND HITCHCOCK 1999; GAGNÉ 2004; PUGLISI 2004; ALBERTI 2013; ALBERTI AND BELLO in press), so that the reader of this note may refer to them.

The present paper once more shows that archaeology is a multifaceted science that should take advantage of the cross-fertilization between diverse artistic and scientific realms, which indeed presently occurs in most cases.

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